

Molecular docking approach for anti-sinusitic activity of pyrrolo[1,2-*a*]pyrazine-1,4-dionehexahydro-3-(phenylmethyl) – extracted from *Streptomyces* sp. VITPK9

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Abstract : Sinusitis is prevalent in children and causes upper respiratory tract inflammation. The aim of the present study was to study the interaction of pyrrolo[1,2-*a*]pyrazine-1,4-dione hexahydro-3-(phenylmethyl) – (PPDHP) extracted from *Streptomyces* sp.VITPK9 (ligand) with selected targets, chemokines involved in the pathogenesis of sinusitis. Three chemokines, Interleukin 1 (1T4Q), Interleukin 6 (1IL6) and Interleukin 8 (3IL8) were chosen as target proteins. Docking was done using PatchDock and the results were analyzed using PyMOL 1.3. The ligand showed least binding energies of -187.98 kcal/mol with 3IL8, -104.08 kcal/mol with 1IL6 and -76.51 kcal/mol with 1T4Q. Interleukin 8, the main chemokine involved in the pathogenesis of sinusitis was found to have strong binding with the ligand among the three chemokines studied. Ours is the first report on the interaction of PPDHP interleukins involved in sinusitis. The results of our study suggest that the compound PPDHP could be a potential agent to target the chemokines that are involved in sinusitis.

Keywords : Docking, pyrrolo[1,2-*a*]pyrazine-1,4-dione hexahydro-3-(phenylmethyl), sinusitis, *Streptomyces* sp.VITPK9.

Introduction

Diseases associated with the sinuses are among the most common health care problems and affect 16% of the human population. They have a significant adverse effect on the quality of daily life¹. Sinusitis is the inflammation of the paranasal sinuses which can be caused by infection (by bacteria, fungi and virus), allergy or autoimmune problems. Opportunistic fungal infections are common in immunocompromised patients². Candidal infection is very common in immunocompromised patients who are also affected with chronic sinusitis. Symptoms of chronic sinusitis may include nasal congestion, night-time coughing, feeling of facial ‘fullness’ or ‘tightness’ that may worsen when bending over, headache and an increase in controlled asthma symptoms in any combinations. Presence of *Candida* species by their characteristic pseudohyphae and yeast form in invasive fungal sinusitis was reported³. Other studies also confirmed the presence of fungal infection in their mucus of chronic sinusitis sufferers (96%).

Interleukins are a group of cytokines that are regulators of host immune response against pathogens, immune response and inflammation. They are necessary in initiating

the inflammatory response to fight diseases. However, excessive inflammation is involved in the pathogenesis of certain diseases. Hamilos studied the cytokine expression in allergic and non-allergic sinusitis and found that the cytokine patterns IL-1 beta, IL-6 and IL-8 were observed in non-allergic sinusitis⁴. IL-8 also known as neutrophil chemotactic factor induces chemotaxis of neutrophil and other granulocytes to the site of infection. Activation of these recruited neutrophils brings about tissue destruction in the local site. Thus IL-8 was played an important role in the pathogenesis of chronic inflammatory airway diseases⁵. About 55% of patients with rhinosinusitis showed IL-8 gene expression in the sinus mucous whereas the control subjects showed no expression⁶.

Natural products serve as a good source for the development of new drugs⁷. Among them, Actinomycetes are the prolific producers of bioactive secondary metabolites^{8,9}. They are a group of Gram-positive bacteria and ubiquitous in nature. The advent of molecular docking has enabled us to predict the biological activity of a particular compound once the target is identified. Docking predicts the preferred orientation of one molecule to a

second when both are bound to each other. It is used to predict the binding of small drug like candidates (ligand) to the protein targets (receptors) in order to assess the affinity of the small molecule¹⁰. Thus docking plays an important role in the rational design of drugs.

The compound PPDHP was extracted from *Streptomyces* sp. VITPK9 isolated from the brine spring of Ningel, Manipur, India was already reported to have anticandidal activity¹¹. Since sinusitis and *Candida* infections are related and hence the present study was aimed at assessing the anti-sinusitic activity of the compound through molecular docking studies.

Results and discussion

The Ramachandran plot analysis of the target proteins 1T4Q, 1IL6 and 3IL8 showed that the most favored regions for these proteins are 87.4%, 73.2% and 93.3%, respectively. The complete plot analysis is given in Table 1. This suggests that the target proteins are excellent choices for docking studies.

The results of the docking were received through email. We got the geometric matching scores, the interface area of the complex, atomic contact energy and the pdb file of the complex which is the predicted complex structure in PDB format. The results are displayed in Table 2.

The schematic representation of the interaction of the lead compound (PPDHP) with the selected interleukins is shown in Fig. 1. The observed geometric matching score for the docked complex of the ligand with 1T4Q is 3572 with atomic contact energy (ACE) of -76.51 kcal/mol.

The contact was with the arginine residue in the 4th position of the target protein. The docked complex of the ligand with 1IL6 shows that the ligand formed hydrogen bond with the threonine in the 44th position of the target protein and the length of the interaction was 2 Å. The geometric matching score was 3772 and the observed ACE was -104.08 kcal/mol. The observed geometric matching score for the docked complex formed by the ligand and 3IL8 was 3566 and the contact was with lysine residue in the 11th position of the target protein. The ACE was found to be -187.98 kcal/mol.

Molecular docking approach was used to predict the interaction of the ligand with target proteins. The anti-fungal effect of the novel compound 4-phenyl-1-naphthyl phenyl acetamide, the CYP 51 inhibitor involved in the synthesis of ergosterol was reported by docking approach¹². A compound isolated from *Streptomyces* sp. VITSVK5 was reported to interact with 14 alpha-sterol demethylase, inhibiting ergosterol metabolism and function thereby exhibiting antifungal activity was reported by molecular docking approach¹³. The anti-*Aspergillus* activity of three compounds isolated from *Streptomyces* sp. VITSTK7 was reported by molecular docking approach¹⁴.

Experimental

The compound PPDHP was extracted from *Streptomyces* sp. VITPK9 which was isolated from soil sediments collected from the Ningel, brine spring located in Thoubal district of Manipur, India. The Simplified Mo-

Table 1. Ramachandran plot analysis of target proteins

Regions on the receptor protein	1T4Q		1IL6		3IL8	
	No. of residues	% of residues	No. of residues	% of residues	No. of residues	% of residues
Most favored regions	118	87.4	115	73.2	56	93.3
Additional allowed regions	17	12.6	32	20.4	4	6.7
Generously allowed regions	0	0	10	6.4	0	0
Disallowed regions	0	0	0	0	0	0

Table 2. Interaction of the ligand with target interleukins

Compound	Target proteins	PDB code	Score	Area	Atomic contact energy	Hydrogen bonds
C ₁₄ H ₁₆ O ₂ N ₂	Interleukin 1	1T4Q	3572	420.80	-76.51	-
	Interleukin 6	1IL6	3772	417.40	-104.08	1
	Interleukin 8	3IL8	3566	405.80	-187.98	-

Fig. 1. Schematic representation of the interaction of the lead compound (PPDHP) with the selected interleukins.

lecular-Input Line-Entry System (SMILES) is a specification in the form of line notation which describes the connectivity and chirality of a molecule. Chemspider is a free chemical structure database from which the canonical SMILES format of the compound was obtained. CORINA is a fast and powerful 3D structure generator using which the pdb file format of the ligand was obtained.

The chemokines Interleukin 1 (1T4Q), Interleukin 6 (1IL6) and Interleukin 8 (3IL8) are involved in the pathogenesis of sinusitis. The protein data bank (PDB) archive contains information about experimentally determined structures of proteins and nucleic acids. The quality of the target protein's structure was analyzed using Ramachandran plot through which the most favored regions for binding was evaluated. The three dimensional structural data and the pdb file format of the chemokines involved were obtained from RCSB Protein Data Bank.

PatchDock is an algorithm used for molecular docking. Two molecules of any type can be the input and the list of probable complexes that can be formed by the two molecules, sorted out by shape and complementarity was obtained as the output. PatchDock available as an online tool in the URL : <http://bioinfo3d.cs.tau.ac.il/PatchDock/> was used for docking studies. The input files are the receptor molecule i.e. interleukins and the ligand molecule, PPDHP. The pdb file formats of the receptor and ligand molecule were uploaded. Clustering RMSD is the value of the RMSD used for final clustering. The higher the

value, smaller the number of results and the recommended value is 4.0 Å. The result would be sent through the e-mail address submitted to them. The results of docking were studied using PyMOL which is an open-source molecular visualization tool used in structural biology which produce high-quality 3D images of small molecules and biological macromolecules such as proteins.

Conclusion

Since the ligand showed least binding energy with IL-8 (3IL8) and it can be used as a potential lead compound for anti-sinusitic activity. To the best of our knowledge this is the first report on anti-sinusitic activity of PPDHP. Based on molecular docking results PPDHP can be used as an anti-sinusitic agent.

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